

A CASE STUDY ON SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF CASHLESS TRANSACTIONS OF INDIA

HEMALATHA K J

Asst. Prof., Research Scholar, University of Mysore, Seshadripuram College, Bengaluru

Sindhu M M

Associate Professor, Commerce Dept., Seshadripuram College, Bengaluru

Abstract:

On 8th November, 2016 Govt. announced Demonetarization in India, which resulted as a challenge to our economy to transform from cash to cashless movement. At time of demonetarization, India had only 2% of cashless under total transactions. Whereas in Singapore -61%, Netherland -60%, France & Sweden- 59%, Canada- 57%, USA- 45%, Japan- 14%, China-10%. Let us know the main problem of why we are falling back in the race of cashless movement. According to survey of 2017, says that 2/3rd of Indian population lays in rural, which as crabbed our cashless system. Mainly over 93% of people in rural haven't used any digital transactions so far. Therefore our real problem lies there. Hence, the researcher is presenting this paper by way of qualitative research methodology and has made an attempt to show how cashless transactions are benefited for our society welfare. The study shows examples of people who have accepted and achieved success in their step.

Key words: Cashless, Successful, Case study, Rural India, Digital payments

I. Introduction

Cashless is generally a financial transaction made through the means of plastic cards, mobile banking, and net banking. Movement is an act of a person for the given situation. Cashless movement is act of a person to do the transactions through digitalized system. In connection with above meaning, it is easy for a common man in India to undergo cashless transactions. But still, India is a vast country having people with different opinions and they also apply their own rights mentioned under Indian Constitution. Hence, to start any movement, especially in India there are certain factors which hinders to implement such system. Therefore, by presenting this paper we have made an attempt to show how cashless transactions are benefited to our Indian Govt. and for society welfare.

This paper studied the different views of people on introducing cashless system in India. The study was conducted by applying descriptive way of research methodology. The successful case study shows that Cashless economy will help in curbing black money, tracking on transactions, reduces cash transactions and helps in improving economic growth by promptly collecting tax to the Government. The major problems of implementing the cashless are cyber fraud, illiteracy, lack of transparency and efficiency in digital payment. The study shows examples of people who have accept and achieved success in their step. In an attempt to encourage poor and illiterate people in rural areas to make digital payments, the government is promoting Aadhaar Pay, which ensures financial transactions by just using fingerprint.

Aadhaar Pay – the merchant version of the Aadhaar-enabled payment system (AEPS), which is already in use – will become an alternative for all online and card transactions which require password and PIN. Through this software app, merchants can take these cashless transactions from a customer who is only required to give their Aadhaar number, name of bank from where the money is to be deducted and their fingerprints for authentication. A Times of India as reported cite, Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI) CEO AB

Pandey said that this app works on any android-based mobile phone, even if lost cost one, with an attached finger biometric device would be help the customers. He further said that “this system ensures digital transactions which do not require card, PIN, there is no need of smartphone for the customers for any transactions”.

II. Research Design

Cashless economy means it is not the complete absence of cash in the economy, it is an economic setting in which goods and services are brought and paid through electronic media. According to the author, Cashless is meant as one in which they are assumed to be no transactions conflict that can be reduced through the use of return. In a cashless economy, the major hand is in rural area rather than in urban area. So government is taking a necessary action for implementing cashless transactions in Rural areas. Let us now discuss about successful case study which took place in Rural areas and now who are happy in enjoying the benefits of cashless system in their location.

To enumerate Successful implementation of cashless transactions in India by way of studying case study who have worked and achieve success place. In one of the interview, Nandan Nilekani, in an interview to Times of India newspaper said , termed this as “a defining point in India moving to cashless”. Shortage of cash has significantly increased the use of digital modes of payment, but the actual shit will only be visible after the cash crunch eases. It is possible that a section of people who has used electronic mode payment for the first time due to the cash dearth will continue to transact through this medium, but there are still a number of problems in making India a cashless economy.

III Objectives of this paper are:

1. To find benefits of cashless transactions
2. To find different kinds of cashless transactions
3. To find solution by narrating case studies on successful implementation of Cashless system in India

IV. Research Methodology

Sources of Data:

Primary Data: Case study discussion

Secondary Data: Collected from Internet and Newspapers.

V. CASE STUDY: Success story of Silk farmers from Vondaraguppe, in India.

Silk Farmer Srinivasaiah

Let us now know how a Silky farmer turned up to cashless and helped the entire village to turn towards cashless environment.

A Place called Vondaraguppe is a sericulture hub and nearly 90% of its households rear silk. For many decades, a person named by Srinivasaiah, never visited a bank as his silk business was done through cash transactions itself. But today all his transactions are turned up to cashless system. Reason is, today he as an ATM card and now he is frequently walking into bank for all transactions. He also adds up his sayings that now what ever he produces when sells he won't accept any cash, instead he transacts only through Cheque. He also says his money is safe now in the hands of bank now.

This work was not so easy for a person to do so, when PM Narendra Modi declared On **8th November, 2016** Demonetarization in India, it was hardship for the Indians to change their system of transaction from cash to cashless. More than urban Rural had hard time to over this situation. But BR Mamatha Gowda Deputy Commissioner of Ramanagara, decided to help her people for going cashless and persuading villager to open bank accounts, which was not easy task to her.

To work on this system she conducted workshops to tell the villagers why its necessary for them to transact

through banks. She also demonstrated how to use a digital system called RuPay. This Powerful woman played a major role in making this happen with full confidence. In return of this workshop conducted people from Silk farmer to Kirana store owner started transforming them to cashless system.

But, Bank manager of Bank of Baroda Mr. Praveen says that the villagers will loss their confidence in cashless system if there is even a small error in functioning of cards or machines, hence, this would become a biggest challenge for the officials.

Silk Farmer Venkatapp S

He also another farmer who sells Silk around 100 kg every month. Where 9 months ago he used to travel for 5 km from his village and sell silk in an auction, and used to come with a feeling of cheated. But after cashless transactions he felt that every transaction is legalized and happy for this kind of evolution.

Silk Farmer Vishakantaiah L

He is also another farmer who grows silk and was a former employee of Karnataka Silk Industries Corporation, says the biggest challenge was to convince villagers their money was safe with the bank and they could withdraw it anytime. He felt that the old practice of stocking up cash at home is no longer prevalent in the village.

VI. Challenges to the Bank officers of Vondaraguppe branch

The employees of Vondaraguppe branch, Bank of Baroda, were going near villagers at 7am to disburse cash since many women and senior citizens cannot come to the bank. The bankers use to the swiping machine to their door step, where they can swipe there Aadhaar and verify their credentials, where their Aadhaar cards are linked to the bank account, so bankers will ensure villagers transactions come to our notice and they don't get cheated.

VII. Benefits of Cashless Implementation in India

For Individuals:

- **Pack of Cards – There** No need to carry any bulky notes in any case. Just carry the required cards or mobile banking will replace traditional banking.
- **More sense of safety** - A PIN protected card, which will work only be with your own credentials.
- **No fear of being robbed** - Unlike carrying cash and letting everyone know that there could be something worth snatching.
- **Tracking of expenses** - It becomes to determine how much was spent where.
- **The exact amount in small denominations can be paid** - Unlike cash transaction, there is no need to pay fringe amount with either of the parties.

For Businesses:

- **Taxation:** With lesser availability of hard cash at home and more in bank account, there is lesser scope of hiding income and evading taxation and when there are more tax payers which will ultimately leads to a lesser rate of taxation for the whole country.
- **Transparency and accountability:** It becomes a very easier to track the flow of money involved in every transaction which will be recorded with the buyer, seller as well as regulatory bodies, making system much more transparent and complaint less. In long term it leads to better business and investment pattern for the company.
- **Higher Revenue:** A derivative advantage of transparent transactions is collection of tax will increase. Thus generating higher revenue for government, which in turn will be converted in to public welfare policies and schemes

- **Lower Transaction costs:** Digital transaction is a boon and boom in terms of processing costs and waiting time. If it is implemented in right way and at right time, it will increase consumption and production rates, which in return will improve the economy

VIII. The List of 11 Digital Payments announced by Narendra Modi as Prime Minister for Indian government to promote digital transactions in India.

- Service tax is Nil on digital transactions / MDR upto Rs. 2000 per transactions.
- Discount of 0.75 % on digital payments at Central Govt Petroleum PSUs
- 2 POS devices will be deployed in each of 1Lakh Villages with population of less than 10,000. Govt through NABARD will extend financial support
- Rural Regional Banks and Co-operative Banks to issue “Rupay Kisan Cards” to 4.32 crore Kisan Credit Card Holders. Govt will support this through NABARD.
- Discount of 0.5% for monthly or seasonal tickets on digital payments from 1st Jan 2017 on suburban railway network
- Free accidental insurance is upto Rs.10 lakh while buying Railways online ticket.
- Public sector banks is advised not to charge more than Rs.100 per month as rental charges for POS terminals/ Micro ATMs/ mobile POS from merchants
- Discount or Credit of upto 10% on the insurance Premium sold through the customer portals of public sector insurance companies on digital payment
- Central Government Departments & PSUs to bear transactions fee/ MDR charges on digital payments, State Governments being advised to do same.
- 10% discount for toll payment on National highways using RFID card/Fast Tags in 2016-17
- Discount of 5% for paying services of catering, accommodation, retiring rooms etc. being offered by railways.

IX. Final Summary:

Just Vondaraguppe’s transform to cashless transactions were allowable by all the villagers. Where silk farmers are accepting payment through cheque, villagers are using RuPay for smaller transactions and obtaining pension funds etc., by swiping their cards. Such cashless mode will bring in much-needed transparency in payments. It, however, remains know if Vondaraguppe can sustain the momentum and move on to complete online payment. As of now, many village traders are waiting for card machines, which will allow those residents to make even everyday purchases with a swiping through machine. This will make it easier for villagers, especially for the old and inform, to buy essential items without having to make frequent trips to the bank to withdraw cash. In order to popularize more use of Aadhaar Pay among merchants in rural side, the government has asked banks them to enroll 30-40 merchants per branch so that they are able to take cashless transactions from customers. For any success, keeping one step forward is required.. That means to improve cashless system in Overall India we need to follow a village in the above case study.

REFERENCE:

1. **Articles from Times Of India**
2. **Internet Information**